

Indian Journal of Gerontology

2020, Vol. 34, No. 3, pp. 313–332

ISSN: 0971–4189, UGC, Care List, Science

The Problems of Elderly Residing in Slums: A Case Study on Siliguri Municipality

Subham Roy and Goutam Mandal

Department of Geography and Applied Geography,
University of North Bengal, Raja Rammohunpur, 734013,
Siliguri, (West Bengal)

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to study the variety of problems and the socio-economic background that related to the 200 elderly people (M=114 & F=86), age varying from 60 years and above, residing in the 10 slums of the Siliguri municipality. These subjects were individually interviewed with the help of an interview schedule. It is found that health-related major problems were faced by 40 per cent elderly, followed by 24.5 per cent had to suffer from financial trouble, 15.5 per cent elderly found social difficulty and about 1.5 per cent elderly faced other problems. Also, there was a close association between gender and types of problems as existing a significant ($p=0.01$) relation among them. Moreover, each problem is further analyzed and discussed in a detailed manner. Based on the present findings it may be recommended that some measures should be taken to fulfill the needs of such elderly people by the state and society.

Keywords: Elderly, Slums, Socio-economic status, Depression, Abuse, Disrespect, Health problems.

Ageing of the population is one of the vital trends and demographic issues of the 21st century, as it is the most inescapable

outcome of demographic transition faced by most countries. According to the UN standard, a country is considered as “Ageing society” or “greying nation” when its proportion of the 60+ population exceeds 7 per cent of the whole population. According to the 2011 census, India shares 8.6 per cent of the elderly population which predicted to increase by 12.6 per cent during 2025. So, within a decade ageing of the population must be a burning issue for policymakers. Furthermore, Vulnerabilities towards the elderly population were increasing with time due to economic dependency, health issues, illiteracy, poor support base, etc. So the main concern is that there needs special attention to the aspects of older people like socio-economic conditions, shelter, health care, safety, and security.

According to Indian ethos and culture, the elderly population always captures a prestigious and superior position in the family. But with increasing technology and modernization, the inter-generational gap was increasing among Indian families which consequences in the increasing distance among old peoples and their grown-up children's. Older people are always holding a prestigious and chief position in the family. But, presently they became feeble, dependent, and queasy in terms of health, economy, and mentally, which lead to many problems for the older people. As the concept of a joint family is changing more into a nuclear family that leads to an anxious situation for elderly people. So this paper tries to analyze the significant problems related to older people who are residing in the slums at the dusk of their life.

Objectives: Following were the major objectives of this study:

1. know about the major problems perceived by the elderly in association with its gender;
2. identify the major financial issue;
3. analysis of the health status and the major types of health issues during old age;
4. to observe is there any depression faced by elderly;
5. How is the attitude of family members towards the elderly;
6. their perception of elderly abuse.

Method

Sample

According to the data from the Urban Poverty Elevation cell (U.P.E cell) of the Siliguri municipality, there are about 187 total slums in the Siliguri municipality, out of which 154 are notified, and 33 are non-notified. So out of these 187 slums in total, ten slums (about 5% sample slum) were randomly selected for this study.

At first, ten slums were selected, and then a pilot survey was conducted to spot the household having at least one elderly person. A total of 200 elderly persons (114 male and 86 female) of age varying from 60 years to above and of both the sexes were selected by the 'Multi-stage random sampling' method from these slum areas for this study.

Selected slum for the study N=200

S. No	Selected Slums	Ward No.	Sample (N=200)		
			Male	Female	Total
1.	Srabannagar	20	16	10	26
2.	Prankrishna colony	28	8	11	19
3.	Purbachal / dhup colony	2	9	7	16
4.	Sahid nagar	43	11	9	20
5.	Pati colony	47	19	10	29
6.	Shitala para	31	10	7	17
7.	Surya sen colony b- block	34	14	9	23
8.	Udayan colony	23	8	8	16
9.	Sukantanagar colony	38	12	10	22
10.	Prakashnagar	42	7	5	12

Tools Used

A structured questionnaire or interview schedule was prepared to collect the various quantitative information related to the problems of elderly residing in slum areas, like socioeconomic background, major problems faced by the elderly, their health status and types of health problems, financial condition, etc. Most of the questions of the questionnaire were close-ended.

These elderly persons were interviewed individually and group interactions were also made. In this process, some information like their relationship with family members, did they face any depression and abuse.

Statistical Analysis

The collected data was prepared on MS-Excel 2007 as a Master table. For further analysis, 'Analystat' software and MS-Excel was used. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were adopted. In the descriptive statistics percentage method, the mean and standard deviation was used to explain the data. Furthermore, in inferential statistics, the Chi-square method (at 0.05 significance level) was utilized to check the association among multiple variables. Also, Pearson's correlation was used to check the relationship.

Results & discussion

Table 1: Socio-economic status of the elderly in association with gender.

Table 1
Association between Gender and Socio-economic Variables of the Elderly Population

Socio-economic background	Gender				Total n=200	Chi-squared value (X ²)	P-value (at Signifi- cance level 0.05)
	Male n1=114	Per- centage	Female n2=86	Per- centage			
Age Group							
60-69 (young old)	47	23.5	41	20.5	88	1.0036	0.6054
70-79 (old-old)	39	19.5	28	14.0	67		
above 80 (oldest-old)	28	14.0	17	8.5	45		
Marital Status							
Married	94	47.0	59	29.5	153	5.5021	0.1385
Unmarried	2	1.0	4	2.0	6		
Widow/widower	17	8.5	22	11.0	39		
Separated/divorced	1	0.5	1	0.5	2		

Cont'd...

Cont'd...

Religion Status							
Hindu	72	36.0	58	29.0	130	0.9	0.8278
Muslim	25	12.5	19	9.5	44		
Christian	13	6.5	7	3.5	20		
Others	4	2.0	2	1.0	6		
Literacy							
Illiterate	22	11.0	45	22.5	67	29.21	0.00
Primary (I-V)	32	16.0	23	11.5	55		
Middle school (V-VII)	29	14.5	9	4.5	38		
High school (VIII-IX)	17	8.5	5	2.5	22		
Secondary (X)	9	4.5	2	1.0	11		
High secondary (XI)	4	2.0	2	1.0	6		
Graduation	1	0.5	0	0.0	1		
Economic Dependency							
Dependent	31	15.5	46	23.0	77	31.88	0.00
Pension	29	14.5	31	15.5	60		
Rent	21	10.5	4	2.0	25		
Presently working	33	16.5	5	2.5	38		
Respondent income (monthly)							
No income	31	15.5	46	23.0	77	23.04	0.00
Below 5000	56	28.0	37	18.5	93		
5000-10000	18	9.0	3	1.5	21		
Above 10000	9	4.5	0	0.0	9		
Living Arrangement of Elderly							
Living alone	12	6.0	8	4.0	20	15.0512	0.01
With spouse only	18	9.0	13	6.5	31		
With spouse only and other members (children's & grand children's)	51	25.5	46	23.0	97		
Without spouse but with married son only	28	14.0	10	5.0	38		
Married daughter	0	0.0	7	3.5	7		

Source: Calculated and compiled by the authors after field survey

Table 2: Major problems reported by elderly in association with gender.

Table 2
Association of Major Problems with Gender

Major Problems	Gender				Chi-square value	P value (at 0.05 sig. level)
	Male (n1=114)	%	Female (n2=86)	%		
Financial problems	37	18.5	12	6.0	11.10	0.01
Health-related problems	51	25.5	29	14.5		
Social problems (including abuse)	12	6.0	19	9.5		
Other problems	2	1.0	1	0.5		
Total (%)	102	51.0	61	30.5		
Grand total (n1 + n2%)	81.5					
No problem	12	6.0	25	12.5		
Total (%)	18.5					

Source: Calculated and compiled by the authors after the field survey.

The data from the above table-2 revealed that 18.5 per cent of the elderly of the sample have no problem with their life, and they live a sheltered and happy life with their family. Among this 18.5 per cent elderly (i.e. 6% male & 12.5% female), most of them were economically independent; also, they keep their health fit and live a respectful life. While poor health condition was more frequently responded by the elderly as one of the major concerns. The vulnerability to sickness increases with advancing age as we know that getting old means slow down in metabolism and our immunity system fails to deal with many diseases. So, about 40 per cent of respondents reported health-related issues, which make them incapable of doing anything and which makes them depressed. Among this 40 per cent elderly, 25.5 are male, and 14.5 per cent were female, so it is clear that male elderly are more susceptible to illness. While about 24.5 per cent of the elderly faced financial crises as with old age, their productivity and outcome at work were almost nil, which results in dependency, and it ultimately brings economic hardship. Among them, 18.5 per cent were male, and 6 per cent were female. Also, problems due to social causes are another

concern of old age. As old age results in worsen health conditions, which increases dependency, and this may affect social life. The above table reveals that about 15.5 per cent of the sample of face problems due to social issues, among them 6 per cent were male, and 9.5 per cent were female. So again, this indicates that female elderly are more victims of a social problem rather than males in slums of the Siliguri municipality. Also, 1.5 per cent of the elderly are those who face some other problems like psychological problems, a problem with accomodations.

Here, the chi-square method was adopted to check the association between various problems of the elderly and how close does it related to gender. Moreover, the result shows high significant (as $p=0.01$, which is <0.05 significance level) relation between various types of problems and gender. As male are more prone to health problems rather than female, also while the dependency among the female is high, so they face more social issues rather than male. In addition to that, as health condition deteriorates male elderly are incapable of earning, this results in more susceptible to the financial crisis in the family.

Table 3: Major Financial Issues Faced by the Elderly.

Table 3
Major Financial Problems

<i>Major financial problems</i>	<i>Gender (N= 49)</i>				<i>Total (%)</i>
	<i>Male (n1 - 37)</i>		<i>Female (n2 - 12)</i>		
		<i>%</i>		<i>%</i>	
Demanding money by children's	5	10.2	3	6.1	16.3
Running out of money	11	22.4	4	8.2	30.6
Low wages/ Poor job	18	36.7	2	4.1	40.8
High cost of health care	1	2.0	3	6.1	8.2
Debt	2	4.1	0	0	4.1
Total		75.5		24.5	100.0

Source: Calculated and compiled by the authors after the field survey

In Table 3 above reveal that among 24.5 per cent elderly (i.e. $N=49$), which is considered as 100 per cent in terms of financial problems. Among this 100 per cent elderly who face financial crisis

only, 75.5 per cent are male, and 24.5 per cent are female as it is already discussed and proved above that male elderly are more vulnerable to financial problems compared to females. About 40.8 per cent of elderly faces problems due to low wages which are caused by poor job quality. Among this 40.8 per cent elderly, 36.7 per cent are male, and 4.1 per cent are female. Besides, about 30.6 per cent of the elderly face problem due to running out of money, which consists of 22.4 per cent male and 8.2 per cent female. Followed by these, 16.3 per cent elderly that they face a financial crisis because their children are forcefully demanding money to their parents which ultimately lead to a shortage of money. Also, 8.2 per cent elderly reported financial issue due to the high cost of health care, among them majority are female, which is about 6.1 per cent, followed by 2 per cent male. Also, 4.1 per cent of only male elderly are in debt.

Table 4: Health conditions of elderly.

Age	Health status (N=200)		
	Good (a)	Average (b)	Poor (c)
60-69	49	23	16
70-79	26	12	29
80 above	8	2	35
Total (N)	83	37	80
Total (%)	41.5	18.5	40
MEAN	27.67	12.3	26.7

Source: Calculated and compiled by the authors after the field survey.

Health is an- vital aspect of ageing. A most crucial matter of public concern is the health condition of the elderly. After newborns and children, older people are most susceptible to morbidity and mortality as health impairment is a function of the aging process. Healthy aged comprises a significant human resource for the growth of the country (Sahu, Chaturbhuj 1998). A healthy life has always been desired and dreamed by all. Being healthy is not just free from any diseases, as it is not just a biological or medical concern but also a significant social and psychological concern. As we discussed above,

that old age slows metabolism, and so older people are more prone to diseases.

According to the Table 4 above, depicts that the maximum mean score, which is 27.67 is towards good health, as the majority of elderly people repeatedly reports pleasant health condition in slums of Siliguri municipality. However, in contrast to that, the mean score of about 26.7, which represent poor health condition, hence it can be said that the vast majority of the elderly are also in dilapidated health condition. So the ratio among good and poor health conditions of the elderly in the slums of the Siliguri municipality is almost 50:50. However, a mean result of 12.3 is under average health, i.e., about that amount of elderly report average health condition.

Also if we look at age-wise health condition than, it reveals that 41.5 per cent of elderly have a good health condition, among them 24.5 per cent is at younger-old age which is in between 60–69 years, followed by 13 per cent at older-old age, i.e., between 70–79 years and only 4 per cent report good health at oldest-old age which is above 80 years. In the case of average health condition, out of 18.5 per cent elderly sample, 11.5 per cent age between 60–69 years, followed by 6 per cent in 70–79 years, and only 1 per cent sample above 80 years have average health. The number of elderly who reported poor health, is about 40 per cent, among them 8 per cent was between the age group of 60–69 years, followed by 14.5 per cent at 70–79 years age group and 17.5 per cent at the oldest age group of above 80 years. So two pictures, was clear from here, that in the younger-old age (60–69 years) elderly have good health condition compared to oldest-old age (above 80 years), and poor health condition mainly dominates at older-old age (70–79 years) and oldest-old age (above 80).

Table 5: Relation between increasing age and deteriorating health.

Age group (x)	60–69	70–79	80+
Poor health (y)	16	29	35

Source: Calculated and compiled by the authors after the field survey.

The above table clearly shows the correlation between increasing age and poor health conditions. As we discussed earlier that most of the elderly face poor health conditions in the age group of 70–79 years and above 80 years. So to prove it, the figure–3 above clearly revealed that as age increases, susceptibility to health problems also intensified. As the ‘*r*’ or *Pearson’s value* which is 0.97, which is near to 1 indicated a highly positive linear relationship between increasing age and deteriorating health condition.

Table 6: Types of health problems among elderly.

Table 6
Types of Health Problems Faced by the Elderly

<i>Types of Diseases</i>	<i>Gender N= 117 (b + c)</i>				
	<i>Male</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Total (%)</i>
Physical problems					
Poor vision	6	5.1	4	3.4	8.5
Hearing	3	2.6	2	1.7	4.3
Weight loss	5	4.3	2	1.7	6.0
Obesity	3	2.6	5	4.3	6.8
Others*	2	1.7	1	0.9	2.6
Total	19	16.2	14	12.0	28.2
Medical problems					
Arthritis (include pain in joints, back, knee, etc)	11	9.4	5	4.3	13.7
Cardio (includes heart problem)	4	3.4	6	5.1	8.5
Respiratory diseases	9	7.7	4	3.4	11.1
Blood pressure	12	10.3	8	6.8	17.1
Diabetes	2	1.7	1	0.9	2.6
Total	38	32.5	24	20.5	53.0
Mental problems					
Anxiety (feelings of worry or fear)	5	4.3	8	6.8	11.1
Dementia (decline in memory, language, problem-solving and other thinking skills)	2	1.7	4	3.4	5.1

*Note: Other problems includes Thyroid, skin problems, and leg swelling.

Source: Calculated and compiled by the authors after the field survey.

According to Table 6 above, it categorizes different kinds of health-related issues faced by the elderly at their old age, and these

various health problems are broadly classified into three primary groups viz. physical, medical, and mental problems. Among these three major categories, many individuals have more than one problem, and also many have all three problems at the same time, so this table is done in a generalized way considering their major problem at the time of the survey. Besides, this table is prepared based on only those elderly who reported their health condition as average, and below average, i.e., about 58.5 per cent (N=117) elderly reported under poor and average health conditions are considered here. The remaining 41.5 per cent (N=83) under good health conditions are excluded.

Thus among physical problems, poor vision is the main issue as reported by 8.5 per cent elderly among which 5.1 per cent are male, and 3.4 per cent are female, followed by 6.8 per cent sample are obese where the female elderly is about 4.3 per cent and 2.6 per cent are male. So this indicates that elderly females face more obese issues than males, about 6.0 per cent face weight loss issues, 4.3 per cent reported a hearing problem, and 2.6 per cent face other problems. In the case of medical problems, blood pressure is a significant problem as reported by 17.1 per cent elderly, among which 10.3 per cent are male, and 6.8 per cent are female. As this high blood pressure is a common phenomenon in old age due to lack of proper diet and food, lack of physical activity, being obese, or weight loss problem. Besides the majority of the elderly of about 13.7 per cent face arthritis problems as because when people were getting old, their joint became weak due to abnormal metabolism or poor immunity system. Problem due to the cardio-related issue was faced by 8.5 per cent sample elderly among them 5.1 per cent are female, and 3.4 per cent are female. Also, 11.1 per cent of the elderly reported respiratory problems and 2.6 per cent face diabetes as a primary issue. While in the case of mental problems, anxiety is a significant concern as reported by 11.1 per cent elderly, among which 6.8 per cent are female, and 4.3 per cent are male. It can be noticed that female elderly are the primary victim of anxiety disorder as due to extreme tension which caused by several factors like poor health problems, the worry of being dependent, anxious about no income, the grief of losing someone, etc. Besides, 5.1 per cent of the elderly report about dementia which can lead to declining in thinking ability and weaken of memory. Also, confusion and poor judgment

capability can be noticed by 2.6 per cent elderly. So in the case of male arthritis, blood pressure, respiratory problem, poor vision, weight losses are some significant problems. While female sample shows cardio-issue, obesity and overall mental problem are some main concern for them.

Table 7: Association among age and health problems.

Table 7
Association between Age and Health Problems

<i>Types of Diseases</i>	<i>Age N=117 (b + c)</i>			<i>Total</i>	<i>Chi-square value (x²)</i>	<i>P value (at 0.05 sig. level)</i>
	<i>60-69</i>	<i>70-79</i>	<i>80+</i>			
Physical problems						
Poor vision	2	3	5	10		
Hearing	1	2	2	5		
Weight loss	5	1	1	7	16.4327	0.03
Obesity	6	2	0	8		
Others	0	0	3	3		
Medical problems						
Arthritis (include pain in joints, back, knee etc)	2	4	10	16		
Cardio (includes heart problem)	6	3	1	10		
Respiratory diseases	2	3	8	13	21.5929	0.00
Blood pressure	5	12	3	20		
Diabetes	0	2	1	3		
Mental problems						
Anxiety (feelings of worry or fear)	5	7	1	13		
Dementia (decline in memory, language, problem-solving and other thinking skills)	1	1	4	6	12.281	0.01
Confusion/Poor judgment	0	0	3	3		

Source: Calculated and compiled by the authors after the field survey.

To know about the relation between varieties of health problems with age, the Chi-square method is applied. Furthermore, the result proved that there is significant relation among age and types of health issues. In all cases of physical, medical, and mental problems the 'p-value' is below 0.05 significance level (i.e. p=0.03, p=0.00, p=0.01)

respectively which clears that with increasing age people are more susceptible to health issues.

Table 8: Depression among elderly

<i>Response</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Total (N=200)</i>
Yes	52	26.0	31	15.5	83
No	62	31.0	55	27.5	117
Reason for depression					Total (N=83)
Loneliness/sadness/boredom	14	16.9	11	13.3	25
Loss of close one	5	6.0	8	9.7	13
Due to health issue	21	25.3	14	16.9	35
Socio-economic causes	7	8.4	3	3.6	10

Source: Calculated and compiled by the authors after the field survey.

Depression is one of the most common infirmities in the elderly population. Among elderly people, chronic diseases, restricted mobility, bereavement, elderly abuse, isolation, and loss of income are major risk factors for depression, in addition to common risk factors in all age groups (Fiske, & Gatz 2009). Depression in elderly persons may have a varied presentation and may be difficult to identify (Mehra, *et al.*, 2017). It has devastating consequences and contributes significantly to misery in this phase of life. The table above reveals that 41.5 per cent of an elderly sample report that they suffer from depression and the remaining 58.5 per cent do not face any depression as they live a happy life. Among these, 41.5 per cent elderly, 26 per cent are male & 15.5 per cent are female, so it is clear that male respondent faces depression more at old age than female. This 41.5 per cent of the elderly sample who report depressions with their life are further being assessed that why they are depressed? This 41.5 per cent elderly who are facing depression further considered as 100 per cent for assessment. Among them, 42.2 per cent of the elderly respondent (N=35), among which 25.3 per cent male and 16.9 per cent female report, depression due to health problems which increase their dependency. About 30.1 per cent sample (N=25), among which 16.9 per cent male and 13.3 per cent female report depression due to

loneliness as they feel alone due to lack of care and negligence. 15.7 per cent elder (N=13), among which 6 per cent male and 9.7 per cent female report depression due to loss of close one as they still miss them and fill low every time. Besides 12 per cent of the respondent (N=10) among which 8.4 per cent male and 3.6 per cent female report depressed due to socio-economic causes.

Table 9: Perception of the elderly regarding the attitude of family members towards them.

Table 9
Opinion of the elderly about the attitude of family members towards them

<i>The attitude of family members towards the elderly</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Total (N=180)*</i>
Respectful	48	26.7	31	17.2	79
Normal	35	19.4	24	13.3	59
Not cordial	19	10.6	23	12.8	42
Recently change in the attitude of family members noticed by the respondent					
Yes	34	18.9	20	11.1	54
No	68	37.8	58	32.2	126
Reason for change in attitude					
	N=54				
Financial cause	12	22.2	4	7.4	16
Due to health problem	19	35.2	8	14.8	27
Others	5	9.3	6	11.1	11

*Note: 20 elderly sample (12 male & 8 female) respond that they live alone, hence no association with family.

Source: Calculated and compiled by the authors after the field survey.

Family life is considered a significant social unit in our society, and this family life is a vital support for elderly peoples. The behavioural patterns of the elderly, their attitudes, and their family constitute a significant aspect of family life. Economic dependency, health problems, unhealthy lifestyles of parents may act as a demotion of their role as head of the family. As consequences, relation, and attitude may change between elderly peoples and their family members. For this analysis, 10 per cent of the elderly who live alone are excluded. So, the table above clearly represents that 43.9 per cent of

the elderly (N=79) have cordial and respectful relationships with their family, among which 26.7 per cent are male, and 17.2 per cent are female elderly. On the other hand, 32.8 per cent of elderly respondent reports that they have average relationships with their family, among which 19.4 per cent are male, and 13.3 per cent are the female respondent.

While 23.3 per cent elderly, among which 10.6 per cent male and 12.8 per cent are female respondents report not cordial or poor relationships with their family. These again show a different attitude of male and female in our society as male always holds a senior-most position in the family and dominates, while in the case of female they always limited in family life. Moreover, after being widow status of women get further demoted in our society, but in contrast, the position of a male after being widower did not mark significant changes.

The entire respondent than asked that whether did they noticed any recent change in attitude or not? About 30 per cent of respondents (N=54), among which 18.9 per cent male and 11.1 per cent female elderly noticed recent changes in attitude and notions of their family members towards them. Moreover, this 30 per cent is considered as 100 per cent in order to further analysis. Interestingly among these respondents who faced significant changes in the attitude of their family members, 29.6 per cent elderly (N=16) among which 22.2 per cent are male, and 7.4 per cent are female report that they noticed changes in inter-personal relation mainly due to financial dependency as they are unable to earn. Hence, they became burden day-by-day as their family members started taunting them. Also, a majority of the respondent of about, 50 per cent report changes in attitude mainly due to their poor health and inability to perform anything productive make their family members exasperate towards them. Among this 50 per cent elderly respondent (N=27), 35.5 per cent are male, and 14.8 per cent are female. Also, 20.4 per cent of the elderly (N=11) report changes in the attitude of family members due to other reasons include poor relationships with family members. So, financial instability and deteriorating health are a primary reason which affects inter-personal relation in old age.

Table 10: Perception about elderly abuse

Table 10
Perception of Elderly Abuse

<i>Victim of Elderly Abuse</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>N(180)*</i>	<i>X²</i>	<i>P value (at 0.05 sig. level)</i>
Yes	27	15.0	34	18.9	61	5.7817	0.01
No	75	41.7	44	24.4	119		

*Note: 20 elderly sample (12 male & 8 female) respond that they living alone did not face any abuse

<i>Types of Elderly Abuse</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>N (61)</i>
Economic Exploitation/ Financial abuse	10	16.4	5	8.2	15
Disrespect/ Verbal abuse/ Emotional torture					
Disrespect/Emotional torture by son	3	4.9	4	6.6	7
Disrespect/Emotional torture by daughter-in-law	2	3.3	7	11.5	9
Disrespect by other family members	0	0	4	6.6	4
Physical(Beating\Slapping)	1	1.6	2	3.3	3
Neglect					
Not giving proper food	3	4.9	3	4.9	6
Not giving proper medicine	4	6.6	4	6.6	8

Source: Calculated and compiled by the authors after the field survey

At the national level, 25 per cent of elders have confirmed they have been a victim of Elder Abuse ever. There was almost no distinction between male and female elders and the city tier-wise trend (Helpage India, 2018). Mistreatment of older people – referred to as “elder abuse” – was first described in British scientific journals in 1975 under the term “granny battering’ (Burston GR, 1975). Elder abuse is defined as “a single or repeated act, or lack of appropriate action, occurring within any relationship where there is an expectation of trust, which causes harm or distress to an older person”. The definition implies that an abusive act towards an older person could be

either an act of commission or omission by any person in a position of trust such as a family member, friend, or neighbour. (NCEA; (2005) identified six categories of elder abuse: (1) Physical Abuse, (2) Emotional Abuse, (3) Neglect, (4) Abandonment, (5) Sexual Abuse and (6) Self-neglect. For broader use, international scholars have agreed upon five categories of elder abuse: (1) physical abuse, (2) psychological abuse, (3) financial abuse, (4) sexual abuse and (5) neglect (Habjanic and Lahe, 2012).

To know about the present status of elderly abuse in the slums of Siliguri municipality, it is asked to every respondent that did they face any abuse or not? Moreover, it is found that about 33.9 per cent elderly (N=61) face some abuse, among which 15 per cent are male, and 18.9 per cent are female. Many of them at earliest did not want to disclose, but after close interaction and later convincing them to keep their identity secret, they somehow broke their melancholy choirs. Here again, those who live alone are excluded.

Furthermore, the chi-square method is applied to check the association between gender and abuses, and it is proved that there exists a significant ($p=0.01$) relation between abuses and gender as a victim. Female elderly who are widows, illiterate, and have no source of income are more vulnerable to abuses rather than males.

Again those 33.9 per cent elderly (N=61) who face abuse are considered as 100 per cent to assess further. Among them, Economic exploitation as abuse is faced by 27.9 per cent (N=17) among which 19.7 per cent are male, and 8.2 per cent are female. This economic exploitation is done by forcefully demanding the elderly to earn or anyhow give financial help to the family, despite the condition of the elderly that they are unable to work or perform anything as their physical health restricts them to do so. About 36.1 per cent (N=22) of elderly in total face disrespect or some verbal mistreatment which is another kind of abuse, among them 11.5 per cent (N=7) faces disrespect or emotional torment by their sons amongst which 4.9 per cent are male, and 6.6 per cent are female elderly. About 18 per cent (N=11) report disrespect by daughter-in-law among which about the majority of about 14.8 per cent are female and 3.3 per cent are male. Also, 6.6 per cent (N=4) of the female elderly only face disrespect or verbal violence by other family members. However, this shows the

fact that the concept of social status among males and females in our society where females face more disrespect or geek-speak than men. A survey of the National level also revealed, 51 per cent elderly, i.e., every second elder opined disrespect amounts most to the Elder Abuse (Helpage India, 2018). Beating and slapping as 4.9 per cent (N=3) respondent faced physical abuse, among which are 3.3 per cent are female, and 1.6 per cent are male. Besides this, data reveals that the elderly face negligence in terms of food and medicine as reported by 23 per cent (N=14) of the elderly in total. Also, about 8.2 per cent of the elderly (N=5) reported that total desertion by their children. So it clears the fact that women in our Indian society face lots of emotions as well as physical torture, negligence, and disrespect compared to men. While in case of economic exploitation, males are more victims. Elderly abuse is an act of demon in our Indian society and also many developing countries. Thus safety and security for the older persons are of utmost need today.

To know more about the opinion of the elderly who are facing abuse, some examples of their broken voices are given below as discussed by them and noted by us (the name was not disclosed to keep them secret, instead alphabetic was used).

Mrs. A “I am a widow and suffering from low blood pressure, my daughter-in-law told me to go back to my village, as she finds me as trouble-maker for the whole family.”

Mr. B “My son fights with me as I am not able to pay for household spending due to no income sometimes, as I am earning as a hawker daily and sometimes earning is almost nil.”

Mrs. C “I need to do all household work from cleaning clothes to cooking food like a servant to get food from my children.”

Mr. D “one day I have a high fever and did not able to go to work; my son beats me and told me as a lethargic and lazy. Moreover, he did not give me food for that whole day”.

Mrs. E “I am a heart patient and need monthly medicine which I buy from my own money that I get as an old-age pension. However, now my daughter-in-law is forcing me to stop those medicines and contribute that money to family expenses”.

Thus it shows that elderly abuses become a major concern for today's society as it revealed that when the elderly are getting old and senile, they became susceptible to health problems and could not earn. All these factors lead to abuse as their children judge them as a burden. So it can be said that elderly people are not protected at their residence as they are getting exploited economically, physically, and emotionally by their kith and kins.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Over recent years the problems related to old age are very attentive among policymakers and researchers. This paper also tries to investigate various issues related to them, especially those who reside in the slums. According to the study, many of them are illiterate, ignorant, and mostly depend on children. Many of them have not enough, substantial income, savings, or property due to which meets all their basic needs became difficult. Health-wise the elderly are suffering from many ailments, as poor health affects the routine life and is characterized by reduced mobility and increased dependency on spouse and children. The frail weak elderly often approach medical facilities and tried balance with family and community. The physical and economic dependence attributed to lesser space in the family. Depression and abuse is another main problem reported by the elderly. Many of the elderly tried to readjust perceptions and behaviours with changing situations. As the family is their world; thus, they rely very much on it for the fulfillment of their primary needs and aspire love, affection, and companion.

Ageing is a part, and its de-generational nature exposes several problems, so more awareness situation for elderly is needed. The government has continued its efforts to introduce various programs for the welfare of the elderly like; National policy on the older person (NPOP) of 1999, the maintenance and protection of parents & senior citizens act of 2007, National council of senior citizens (NCSrC) of 2012, etc. Also, NGOs have played a significant role in highlighting many problems related to old age and also gave many solutions to it. Except for efforts from government and NGOs, economic security for the elderly is the most appropriate tool to deal with many problems as it makes them independent. Proper health care facilities like a free

health checkup, rehabilitation centres, community or home-based disability efforts must be provided. To, protect from abuse awareness generation programs must be adopted, and strict law should be implemented. Also, positive and cheerful thought in old life was necessary to fight against depression. Except for all these adequate policy initiatives & its implementation, welfares and developmental programmes for aged would help them free form many fear and negativity of getting old, and provide them with a meaningful, active healthy and happy old age.

Acknowledgment: The authors would like to express their sincere gratitude to many unnamed older people of the slums of Siliguri.

References

- Burston, G.R. (1975):Letter: Granny-battering; *Br Med J.* Sep 6; 3(5983): 592.
- Fiske, Amy and Gatz, Margaret (2009): Depression in Older Adults; *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology* 5(1): 363–89.
- Habjanic A, and Lahe D. (2012). Are frail older people less exposed to abuse in nursing homes as compared to community-based settings? Statistical analysis of Slovenian data. *Archives of Gerontology and Geriatrics*. Vol. 54, No. 3, pp. 261–270.
- Help-Age India (2018). *Elder Abuse in India: Changing Cultural Ethos & Impact of Technology* . New Delhi.
- Mehra, Aseem', Sandeep Grover, Subho Chakrabarti, and Ajit Avasthi (2017) Symptom profile of depression in elderly: Is assessment with geriatric depression rating scale enough? *Jr. of Geriatric Mental Health*, Vol. 4, No. 1, pp. 18–25.
- Sahu, Chaturbhuj (1998): *Problems of Ageing Among Indian Tribes*; Sarup & sons, New Delhi.